

XN002 Building a National High-Resolution Geophysics Reference Collection for 2030 Computation

ARDC CROSS-NCRIS PROGRAM PROJECT FINAL REPORT

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1 PROJECT INFORMATION

INVESTMENT ID	XN002
PROJECT START AND END DATES	June 2021 - June 2023
LEAD ORGANISATION	Australian National University (ANU)
PARTNER ORGANISATIONS	National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) Australia AuScope Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (TERN)
PROJECT CONTACT PERSON	Dr Ben Evans

1.1 Background

Large volumes of geophysical data have been acquired by Universities, Industry, and Federal/State/Territory Government agencies since 1950. Historically, the rawer forms of data (processing levels L0-L1) have been hard to access due to the inability to manage and analyse data at scale. As a result, released data have been highly processed and reduced, and then accessible only as file downloads or visualisations. In recent years, some L0-L2 geophysical datasets have been progressively organised at the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI), with associated High Performance Computing (HPC)/High Performance Data (HPD)-enabled codes. This includes datasets where the acquisition, and/or instruments used to collect the data were funded by AuScope.

This project, “Building a National High-Resolution Geophysics Reference Collection for 2030 Computation”, hereafter referred to as Geophysics 2030, was a joint project between the the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI), AuScope, Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN) and the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) (<https://doi.org/10.47486/XN002>).

To support next-generation geophysical research at scale, valuable datasets and associated metadata need to be captured in machine-readable formats and leverage international standards, vocabularies and identifiers. Making the raw and high-resolution versions of cross-NCRIS network data fully FAIR compliant and integrated with existing (largely federal and state government) datasets were the major challenges of this project. The focus was on ensuring high-resolution datasets would be suitable for programmatic access in high-performance computing (HPC) environments and to lay the foundations for more rapid data processing by 2030 next-generation scalable, data-intensive computation, including artificial intelligence/machine learning, data assimilation and data analysis.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

The Geophysics 2030 project aimed to create a nationally transparent geophysics data system suitable for programmatic access in high-performance computing environments at NCI. The focus was on Magnetotellurics (MT), Passive Seismic (PS) and Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) datasets collected with AuScope funding, or using instruments funded by AuScope. The raw and high-resolution versions of the time series data have been progressively organised at NCI, with associated HPC/HPD-enabled codes. This will enable a new era of geophysical research including multi-physics (re)processing, modelling and analysis at scale with the computational tools available within the NCI. Datasets were reviewed according to the FAIR and CARE principles and enriched with detailed metadata, such as internationally recognised identifiers, lineage statements and FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs).

The project has achieved key aims for the Geophysics 2030 collections including:

1) ***Vertical integration from source datasets to derivative products***

The Geophysics 2030 datasets have been ingested, curated and published via NCI’s infrastructure. Rarer and minimally processed forms of MT, PS and DAS data are now accessible on HPC as well as selected higher-level data products. MT data have been ‘vertically’ integrated, such that the source datasets are

associated with processed data products at NCI as well as other derivative data products hosted by external data portals.

2) ***Horizontal integration of remotely sensed datasets with observational datasets for better calibration***

‘Horizontal’ integration has been enabled by structuring the Geophysics 2030 datasets to support integration of disparate datasets that can be accessed in real time as online web services from other repositories. For example, different remotely sensed datasets can now be integrated with time-stamped observational point-located datasets available as web services anywhere to create more precise, better calibrated data products, answering novel research questions and accelerating research innovation.

3) ***Using HPC enables raw data to be easily processed, and derivative products more readily generated***

Capturing and curating the packed raw instrument collected data, Level 0 and Level 1 time series geophysical data products is critical to support next-generation research. With accurate metadata, the rawer data can be reprocessed and reanalysed quickly. This empowers researchers to generate their own derivative data products fine-tuned to their precise exact requirements (e.g., Level 2 transfer functions) and supports transparency, reproducibility and reuse of their products. It ensures the maximum utility is obtained from these unique field collections.

A review of international community-preferred standards for raw and derivative data/metadata in various geophysical disciplines was conducted. For MT, raw datasets have been carefully curated and organised to support processing in an HPC-enabled environment and the creation of dirt-to-desktop workflows.

4) ***FAIR enabled, including improving the data citation and information collecting metrics***

All the Geophysics 2030 collections have been documented with FAIR-compliant metadata, leveraging international standards, identifiers, and vocabularies to better enable citation including recognition of funding by stakeholders and other roles in the collection and generation of the data. Use of identifiers also enables impact assessment planning to be completed and mechanisms have been tested to track usage of the collections over time. Although the aim was to make Geophysics 2030 datasets both human and machine actionable, lack of agreed standards (in particular vocabularies) being applied to the datasets still meant that some manual wrangling of the data and metadata was required.

2 DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT OUTPUTS

2.1 Achievements against project work packages:

Note: During the course of the project, we used a fourth option: that is, the planned scope of work was adjusted and while some parts could not be strictly classed as fully completed, there was no impact on the Project Outcomes. For example, some milestones in the 2030 Geophysics Collection Project were designed to test innovations available elsewhere, but soon discovered that the available technology/infrastructure was not mature enough to support the original ambitions. To comply with the integrity of the traffic-light status, these particular milestones have been noted as completed in the Status Column, and in the column on details of progress have been marked “**Completed as far as possible**”. Any milestones labelled as such were not considered to impact on the overall project outcomes and in the Status column they are listed as “Completed”.

WORK PACKAGE	DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION	DATE COMPLETED
Work Package 1 - Data ingest and organisation		

<p>1.1 First major survey of all raw and other derivative, associated or other higher-processed data from AuScope's funded or part-funded Magnetotelluric (MT) and Passive Seismic (PS) instruments/data acquisition programs. The first survey will particularly look at the university-partnerships but may necessarily extend to other datasets that are directly related (for example, AusLAMP, AusARRAY, AusPASS). It will also look at newer forms of data such as DAS being pioneered in the AuScope-university domain. The survey is to include the contact's name and the organisation that has a copy of the raw data. The survey is to include a priority, and readiness/suitability for NCI (including location and state of field metadata), as well as the storage capacity required at NCI.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): AuScope completed a survey in December 2021 of all Geophysical Data that they have funded. The classification of “funded by AuScope” was determined as either a survey funded by AuScope and/or data collected using an instrument funded by AuScope. The full survey is available here: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1xL5hZEISrQ9BvJnOaVK4NFAFICvrvipfjilLnHI3-3wQ/edit#gid=0 Subsequent to this survey, the AuScope co-funded collection of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) data started at RSES was included.</p>	<p>Dec 2021</p>
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<p>1.2 Selection of the first tranche of candidate data, and establish a data directory structure for each of the AuScope MT and PS.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): The Packed Raw Field AusLAMP MT time-series data in the Musgraves, South Australia and Tasmania have been selected and will be translated into new standards in parallel with the translation of the NSW MT AusLAMP dataset by GA.</p> <p>Discussions are underway for mirroring the RSES AusPASS Passive Seismic Data Collection to NCI.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): The ASTER dataset was added to the first tranche of candidate data.</p> <p>New directory structures have been set up for AuScope funded PS and MT data in the AuScope Data space. New directory structures for MT have been documented and we are in the process of implementing these directory structure changes. They are almost complete.</p>	<p>Dec 2022</p>
<p>1.3 Refresh survey for any additionally discovered raw, derivative, or associated datasets or other classes of datasets of high priority. This will particularly address partnerships with GA, and also expand the survey to a first cut of other geophysical types that would be part of a national integrated high-resolution reference collection (magnetic, gravity, AEM, radiometrics, INSAR, GRACE, ASTER) and the National Virtual Core Library (NVCL); The survey, together with the NCIs data release process, will also inform AuScope on improvements to data management policy to improve into the future.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): The ASTER data will be included as a hyperspectral dataset. A related hyperspectral dataset, the NVCL is part of the AuScope Phase 2 Data Retention Program project which will also be hosted at NCI. This will mean that there will be 3 different hyperspectral data collections (ground measurements, satellite and borehole) accessible at NCI.</p> <p>For PS, MT and DAS, there needs to be agreement on common geophysical data formats that will make the data fully interoperable.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Survey is complete for data that will be added, and location of derivative datasets added.</p>	<p>Aug 2022</p>

<p>1.4 Ingest of first tranche of data for each of MT and PS raw datasets - <i>particularly focused on the AuScope-University partnerships</i>. The Dataset is organised on the filesystem so that it can be processed with computational tools within NCI, which may be either ready for users, or ready to be minimally reprocessed or transformed to make into an updated format and version.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): The first tranche of AuScope MT raw data has been made available on NCI. The new international metadata standard (mt_metdata) and data format (MTH5) for MT is being considered.</p> <p>The complexity of requirements is being discussed further between NCI, AuScope, GA, USGS, IRIS, UNAVCO, GFZ Potsdam, Université Grenoble Alpes, ETH Zurich. A consensus is expected in November 2022. A new data transfer format was announced at EGU on 27 May, the implications for the project are being discussed.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): The my80 directory structure is being developed, taking into consideration the need to give continuity of service to existing users and update/align existing services including catalogue, DOIs, user documentation and harvesting to Research Data Australia (RDA).</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): First tranche of MT data has been transferred and organised on the NCI gdata filesystem under project code my80.</p>	<p>May 2023</p>
<p>1.5 Milestone Report 1 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): As per advice of ARDC, UAT will be reported for the whole project.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): <u>A first set of User Acceptance Tests (UATs)</u> were created and designed around: 1. Viewing and downloading Geophysics 2030 related metadata from the NCI Data Catalogue and RDA; 2. Accessing Geophysics 2030 data from the NCI THREDDS Data Server.</p> <p><u>A second set of UATs</u> formulated around accessing Geophysics 2030 data in-situ on HPC using <u>NCI's Geophysics Specialised Environments</u> were also developed.</p>	<p>Jun 2023</p>
<p>1.6 Refresh survey leading into the selection of second tranche of data</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): AuScope and NCI conducted a review of the next stage of data.</p> <p>Progress Report 1 (November 2022):</p>	<p>June 2022</p>

<p>1.7 Selection of second tranche of candidate data, including any updates to directory structures, updated versions, and/or derivative data now reprocessed from the earlier raw data using any new common pipelines and tools from WP5.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Second tranche datasets have been selected and include AusPass and MT Data from Tasmania.</p>	<p>Nov 2022</p>
<p>1.8 Ingest of data for each of MT and PS raw datasets, <i>particularly focused on the AuScope-GA partnership, plus additional data from university partnerships</i>. The Dataset to comply with user acceptance tests (UAT); that the data organised on the filesystem so that it can be processed with computational tools within NCI and ready for other forms of data access through publication.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Ingest of raw data being planned.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Second sets of data chosen: MT: Packed Raw Tasmania AusLAMP time-series data. PS: The underlying time series datasets from the AusPass portal have been moved to NCI and projects set up. Directory structures are being implemented.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): All data is in the NCI Catalogue. AusPass is now mirrored to NCI as is and there are now systematic monthly updates.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>1.9 Milestone Report 2 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Not started.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): The first set of <u>UATs</u> were completed and <u>results documented</u>. A 96% pass rate was obtained; some ideas for future developments/enhancements were noted.</p> <p><u>The second set of UATs</u> were sent out to two users for testing and feedback. The two testers came back with very positive reports about accessing the Geophysics 2030 data in-situ on HPC using our NCI Geophysics environments.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>1.10 Refresh survey for any additional discovered raw or derivative datasets, <i>particularly focused on the State Government partnerships, plus additional data from GA- and University partnerships or processing pipelines</i>. Select the next tranche of data ready to be ingested.</p>	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Completed: third tranche of data sets to be transferred identified.</p>	<p>Nov 2022</p>

<p>1.11 Selection of the third tranche of candidate data, and establish a data directory structure for each of the AuScope MT and PS.</p>	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): The third tranche of data will be: 1) the Level 0 & Level 1 Musgraves MT time series data in the mth5/mt_metadata format and the Level 2 Musgraves transfer functions (GSSA will be publishing in their portal as well) - NCI will publish with more intuitive naming convention. See https://magix.dmirs.wa.gov.au/surveys/view-survey/3804 which contains a link to https://geodownloads.dmp.wa.gov.au/downloads/geophysics/72444/).</p> <p>2) the Packed Raw GSSA AusLAMP MT time series dataset 3) the Packed Raw Tasmania Broadband MT time series dataset 4) the DAS data - under an embargo until 2024. We will publish a landing page, but users will only be able to access the data if RSES approves their membership to the DAS project.</p> <p>Directory Structures are being established.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023):</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>1.12 Ingest of data for each of the MT raw and PS raw dataset, <i>particularly focused on partnerships with each of the relevant State government agencies but including any remaining university partnerships and GA.</i> Expect to now have mapped the coverage and issues of obtaining the raw datasets with ability to reference highly processed derivative datasets to the raw form. The Dataset to comply with NCI collection and user acceptance tests (UAT) - both QA/QC and processing/analysis tools from WP3: the data organised on the filesystem so that it can be processed with computational tools within NCI.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): We have approached GSSA to move their SA AusLAMP time series data to the NCI gdata filesystem. Unfortunately, most of the time series datasets are on hard drives or restricted-access cloud stores. Discussions are also underway with GSSA and MRT to differentiate the rawer data for future use.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Raw data associated with the GSSA AusLAMP surveys and PS now published to the NCI Data Catalogue. See: 1. Magnetotelluric surveys of South Australia as part of the Australian Lithospheric Architecture Magnetotelluric Project (AusLAMP): https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/bzd5-n780 2. AusPass Passive Seismic Collection: https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/zyay-2g34</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

<p>1.13 Final Report contribution: including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Setting up UAT read for testing in Q2 2023.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): The first set of <u>UATs</u> were completed and <u>results documented</u>. A 96% pass rate was obtained; some ideas for future developments/ enhancements noted.</p> <p><u>The second set of UATs</u> were sent out to two users for testing and feedback. The two testers came back with very positive reports about accessing the Geophysics 2030 data in-situ on HPC using our NCI Geophysics environments.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
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<p align="center">Work Package 2: Data Repository coordination and updates</p>		
<p>WORK PACKAGE</p>	<p>DETAILS INCLUDING EXPLANATION OF ANY VARIATION</p>	<p>DATE COMPLETED</p>
<p>2.1 First review of relevant data registries (NCI, Research Data Australia, AuScope, TERN, GA, CSIRO, and state surveys): how it is currently recorded, if it is FAIR compliant at the dataset level (e.g., has a DataCite DOI) and where changes will need to be made. Gaps and inconsistencies will be identified, and priority issues targeted for remedial action (e.g., no reference to AuScope funding or data), duplicate or inconsistent copies of separate distributed copies of data, and where it would be preferable to reference a master version on NCI - such as raw or processed data.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): The review has noted general consistency between NCI, AuScope, TERN and CSIRO on metadata compliance, use of DOIs and FAIR, yet there are substantial metadata inconsistencies between and within the government agencies: DataCite DOIs, ORCID, ROR and other GUPRIs are not routinely used.</p> <p>None have reference to AuScope Funding. Additionally, different levels of processing and formatting are referenced differently within and between the groups. Differentiation of the same products between different catalogues registries is poor.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Decision made to use Research Data Australia as the catalogue where the metadata for datasets from NCI, GA and AuScope are all aggregated. Unfortunately, the GSWA, GSSA and MRT catalogue are not harvested by RDA, neither are they hosted by state data.gov.au groups. The overheads are too high for this aggregation to be done by NCI, and it would be simpler if RDA could harvest directly from the state and NT geological surveys.</p>	<p>Nov 2022</p>
<p>2.2 Publish NCI catalogue metadata for the first tranche of release of MT and PS data from WP1. The release complies with NCI repository standards including discoverable in the NCI catalogue and a DOI at the dataset level, a visible licence, access constraints and location of data.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): MT data needs to be updated due to change of recommended international standard in January 2022.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): MT Musgraves Packed Raw Time Series Data and ASTER complete and ready to be published.</p>	<p>Feb 2023</p>

<p>2.3 Milestone Report 1 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): First tranche of MT data has passed acceptance by ARDC (UAT). See Section 8 for FAIR.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): UAT will be completed for the whole package, see section on FAIR.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023) Combined UAT report completed at project conclusion.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>2.4 Trial harvest into Research Data Australia, which reflects the changes at NCI (including datasets from WP1).</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): In progress - NCI currently has one collection (University of Adelaide Magnetotellurics Data Collection) harvested into RDA and working with ARDC for harvesting of additional collections relevant to the project.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): In progress: additional NCI collections (including those associated with the Geophysics 2030 project) have been harvested into the RDA Demo environment and are in the final stages of preparation for production release. Source metadata from the NCI Data Catalogue has been updated and mappings/decision rules have been recently reviewed to ensure that various metadata elements display correctly in RDA, including: Creators, Year of publication, DOI, Access rights and Licence</p>	<p>Feb 2023</p>
<p>2.5 First review and a prioritised plan of horizontal integration - (e.g. between repositories that have a higher level product but need to reference the data at NCI - e.g. rawer form). Prioritise candidates for improvements such as TERN calibration data with NCI holdings (e.g., hyper-spectral and other geophysical types in any exiting NCI collection), other AuScope programs (particularly AusPASS for processed data from the rawer data, and NCVL), GA, CSIRO and state surveys. Provide a plan for both a) any improvements on the fidelity of datasets within existing collections and the use of identifiers or other forms of lineage tracking, and b) provide any recommendations for improvements to Identifiers work in (WP3).</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Good progress made with metadata and data comparison with TERN.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Rethinking this as metadata is too heterogeneous between the relevant organisations, and in some cases, is highly variable within an organisation and there is no consistency across internal projects and groups. Crosswalk between the groups and classic metadata profiles used by others: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/160ZA-arawodR5U0JavfVgxLy0IBMfGG E/edit#gid=1041585694</p> <p>NCI has agreed to move on GeoNetwork upgrade - this will need to be in place before updating records.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): GeoNetwork upgrade is in progress. In the interim, available identifiers have been added to the Geophysics 2030 records (e.g., RORs, ORCIDs and grant IDs, where available).</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>2.6 First implementation of priority identifiers provided in WP3</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Will be done at the upper collection level.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Delayed because of a known gap in the Crossref organisational membership issue, but should be achievable at the collection level. DOI DataCite for collection; ORCIDs for people; RORs for orgs. ARDC Investment Crossref DOI included so far. Other Grant IDs - to be determined how/when to include. All funding organisations are included, but no Grant ID itself is linked because they are not available.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

	<p>Final Report (June 2023): We have made the decision not to use Crossref Grant ID. NCI and AuScope do not have the infrastructure to support this. Grant IDs could be done through DataCite.</p>	
<p>2.7 Milestone Report 2 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and (if appropriate - lodgement under FAIR)</p>	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): UAT will be reported collectively.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Combined UAT report completed at project conclusion.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>2.8 Review and revise the list of other higher-processed data derived from AuScope funding. Where appropriate notify others of data that needs to reference the data at NCI, and/or could be retired by using the updated NCI copy.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): We are holding discussions with GSSA and MRT as to how the rawer data at NCI can be referenced in their catalogues.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): MRT has updated relevant catalogue records to reference the data products available via NCI. GSWA is also now referencing the collection.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>2.9 Second implementation of priority identifiers provided in WP3</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): On track.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Where available, existing grant ID references have been added to Geophysics 2030 records and made available in the ISO 19115 metadata.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>2.10 Revise harvest into Research Data Australia, which reflects the changes at NCI - both for WP1 and WP3</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): On track.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Updated metadata available for harvesting into RDA. Identifier changes now feeding through to RDA.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>2.11 Final Report contribution: including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Final Report (June 2023): UAT was completed in conjunction with WP#1 & WP#3 (See summary).</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

Work Package 3: Identifiers

Deliverable Description	Progress details	Actual
<p>3.1 From the WP1 and WP2 surveys, review and map the 1) relevant funders and funding and how they can be referenced from NCI. This includes AuScope, NCI, NCRIS, ARC, CSIRO Federal and State surveys, Industry that were identified in WP1 survey and 2) the attribution roles to staff/researchers (e.g., ORCID, ROR)</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): NCI, AuScope and TERN currently do not use Crossref DOIs for funding as they are not members of Crossref. We are awaiting the outcome of work by ARDC to see if a consortium can be set up for NCRIS facilities to mint Crossref DOIs similar to the ARDC DataCite Consortium. GUPRI identifiers such as ORCID, ROR, DataCite DOIs, etc are not routinely used by the government agencies.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Project can only use Crossref if NCI, TERN and AuScope each become direct members. An alternative is to just use handles and list in the RDA Projects and grants page. Decision not made yet.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Inclusion of handles was unsustainable and unsuitable for requirements given infrastructure overheads (and given pending decisions from DataCite regarding support for grant identifiers). Through this project, a detailed investigation and analysis of identifiers used for funders, grants and creator/contributor roles was completed. Internal templates and exemplar metadata records were created to guide metadata capture and development work. In addition, all the Geophysics 2030 metadata records were updated to list 1) associated funding agencies (including RORs); 2) detailed credit/acknowledgement statements, as appropriate and; 3) grant identifiers (e.g., ARC PURLs, ARDC Grant IDs/DOIs), where available. Identifiers have been captured and stored in the current back-end catalogue database in preparation for pending upgrades to NCI infrastructure (GN/19115-1 upgrades).</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>3.2 First review of the end-to-end process for recording, citation and then the analysis of cited data to gather metrics. The review includes the role of Crossref (including Crossref Event Data), SciVal, Scholix, DataCite, Grant ID, ROR and journals metric gathering processes.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Awaiting ARDC decision on potential Crossref consortium before proceeding. In addition, NCI is currently reviewing its backend database that currently only takes ORCIDs. NCI is keen to expand this to other identifiers but will wait until the decision is made on how to implement Crossref DOIs before proceeding.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): ARDC cannot provide a consortium for Crossref Grant IDs, still researching alternatives.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): See response to 3.1. All Geophysics 2030 metadata records have been assigned DOIs in order to facilitate future usage tracking; the ARDC Grant DOI for the Geophysics 2030 project has been added into all the Geophysics 2030 records in the credit/acknowledgement statement.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>3.3 Milestone Report 1 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not ready for UAT and See Section 8 for FAIR.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023):</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

	Combined with UAT for WP#2.	
3.4 First implementation of the identifiers and running the citation process	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Will be done at the uppermost collection level</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): At the highest level there will be no more than 6 collections, and these can be filled manually. DOIs are being implemented per data collection and ORCIDs. where possible.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Analysis has revealed that NCI citations are not being identified through the citation process due to at least 7 or more reasons:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Researchers may not put the DOI for the dataset in the scholarly publications: not all publications ask for or even accommodate this. 2. Data is published in 2022-2023 and given that the publishing pipeline takes approximately 12-24 months, the Geophysics 2030 outputs are unlikely to be visible in citations for at least 2 years. 3. There are known difficulties with data citations within earth science journals failing to be included in common citation metrics platforms such as SciVal/Scholix (see: https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=2025364&HistoricalAwards=false). Members of 2030 are participating in the group that is trying to solve this. 4. Researchers frequently only submit to journals the processed/derivative data products that their publication is based on, rather than specifically citing the underlying data downloaded from NCI that was used as a source for their data product. 5. Journals currently limit the number of identifiers that can be cited in a single paper to 10 or up to 20 citations. On HPC it is common practice to aggregate many more datasets into a “data collection”. The newly created collection can have a DOI, but current practices will not enable individual datasets to be picked up by common citation metrics platforms. This has led to the formation of the RDA Complex Citation Working Group which members of the 2030 team are participating in (see https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citations-working-group). 6. Web scraping of NCI service endpoints and re-publication in alternative data portals is a known issue that impacts on the use of NCI DOIs/citations: several sites do not even publicly acknowledge that the data is sourced at NCI, nor do they reference the NCI DOI, licence or owner of the dataset (which may or may not be NCI). 7. The publication process is a complicated triangle between the Publisher, the Repository and the researcher and requires interaction between all three to ensure that the actual version and correct DOI of the dataset is released with the date of release of the scholarly publication. This requires that during the peer review process, the dataset is embargoed and only made accessible to the reviewers, which creates a complexity on the researchers. A new RDA Working Group on Coordinating ESES Data Preservation and Scholarly Publication Processes is being proposed (https://docs.google.com/document/d/14aZqQwWAMwLEUwR7XN7WQ3i 	June 2023

	OwSLX55XohCDESENVtb6l/edit#heading=h.fikikhfv6zln) and members of the 2030 project are participating in this.	
3.5 Trial and review of end-to-end process for citation and metric gathering based on WP2	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Start made.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Need Counter to be completed, but this has been delayed. We have been analysing Counter and considering its limitations in the context of the project.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): NCI has documented why this is not possible. See WP#3.4 and WP#7.</p>	June 2023
3.6 Milestone Report 2 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and (if appropriate - lodgement under FAIR)	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Not enough implemented to do testing</p> <p>May 2023: Combined with UAT for WP#2.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Combined UAT report completed at project conclusion.</p>	June 2023
3.7 Second implementation of the identifiers and running the citation process	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Still sorting out identifiers.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): <i>Completed as far as is possible, noting limitations discussed in WP#3.4 and WP#7.</i></p>	June 2023
3.8 Second review of end-to-end process for citation and metric gathering	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Metric gathering is starting to be in place.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023):</p>	June 2023
3.9 Final Report contribution: including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR	<p>Final Report (June 2023): Combined with UAT for WP#2. Combined UAT report covered testing access to identifiers; UAT passed.</p>	June 2023

Work Package 4: Geophysics Data Standards

Deliverable Description	Progress details	Completed
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<p>4.1 Review the international data standards (MT, PS, DAS, Hyperspectral, other geophysical types - mag, grav, AEM, radiometrics) that should be used for the raw and derivative data, and suitable for research. Make a first candidate selection that can be used and evaluated for the project. The data must be in a suitable self-describing HPC format for processing by tools to be used by WP5 and can be established in an automated reprocessing pipeline. Part of the acceptance is that the data can be readily revised/augmented based on further updates throughout the project.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): A review has been undertaken of international standards used for geophysical data sets and are available in this document: Geophysics 2030 metadata standards and data formats</p> <p>Conversion of AusLAMP Musgraves MT time series dataset into the new mt_metadata compliant MTH5 file(s) was started but considerable difficulties were encountered within the new standard itself when applied to existing data. The new standard has 370 elements, of which 272 are mandatory. It is impossible to compile these for legacy datasets. A meeting of the Australian MT Practitioners' group was held on June 20 to try to develop an agreed AusLAMP profile of the mt_metadata standard for legacy data.</p> <p>At a meeting of the Australian MT Community on August 3, a minimum legacy metadata profile of the international standard was proposed to the whole Australian MT Community (see this spreadsheet - sheet 5 is the proposal).</p> <p>The intention is to include the MT-metadata vocabulary in RVA. USGS would like to explore creating the identifiers in a USGS name space. We would also need to publish the legacy metadata profile for the AusLAMP national data set as proposed by this project.</p> <p>Completed as far as possible.</p>	<p>Feb 2022</p>
<p>4.2 Review domain-specific vocabulary standards (e.g., EMAC, FDSN) and how the collections might use either an ARDC vocab service, or infrastructure fit-for-purpose at NCI</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): A review has been undertaken of international metadata standards for geophysical data sets and are available in this document: Geophysics 2030 metadata standards and data formats.</p>	<p>Feb 2022</p>

<p>4.3 Consultation with Stakeholder groups - AuScope project leaders (e.g., SAM), Industry, Federal and State Surveys</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Meeting held with GA and 2030 on AusLAMP metadata and workflows. Meeting minutes are available here.</p> <p>Unfortunately, on May 27 at the European Geophysical Union conference, IRIS and UNAVCO announced a completely new standard for Seismic, geodetic and other data: the implications of this are now being assessed by the project in consultation with AuScope and Geological Survey Geophysicists. Meetings are underway with stakeholder groups on how to deal with the change in standards, but it is hopeful that delays will not be too significant. The fall-back position is that we make the data available in the current standard.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): In progress - meeting regularly with the US developers of the MT standard.</p> <p>Workshop on MT At the Frontiers of HPC organised with key stakeholders in industry, academia and government - https://www.eventbrite.com.au/e/mt-at-the-frontiers-of-hpc-tickets-441413849707</p> <p>This workshop was held on 25 October 2022 and aimed to get the balance between future directions and what has to be delivered now. Also, we seek feedback on issues people may be having with data access on HPC currently.</p> <p>Follow-on workshop accepted for AEGC in March 2023: "Scaling MT acquisition, processing, interpretation, and people" workshop.</p>	<p>Oct 2022</p>
<p>4.4 Milestone Report 1 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): UAT with the relevant scientific advisory committee is underway and See Section 8 for FAIR.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): UAT will be done across the whole project</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): UAT to be combined with WP#2.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

<p>4.5 First revision of data specifications that is aligned with modern international research and HPC/D requirements, and can be supported under the existing tools under WP5</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Partly delayed due to international change in standard.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Software has been developed to automate the generation of Level 0 and Level 1 mth5 files with mt_metadata. We are waiting on certain parameters (e.g. funder, state, institution/agencies, adding in CC-BY-4.0 to copyright.release_license controlled vocabulary, etc.) to be added/updated to the mt_metadata code base before finalising the publication of The AusLAMP Musgraves Province Level 0 and Level 1 mth5/mt_metadata files.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): The <u>MagnetoTelluric time series data publication v1 (MTtsdp_v1)</u> codes were developed for generating Level 0 and Level 1 MT time series products in the MTH5/mt_metadata format.</p> <p>Additionally, <u>codes were developed</u> to run MT time series processing at scale for the Musgraves time series MTH5/mt_metadata dataset on the NCI Gadi supercomputer.</p>	<p>Mar 2023</p>
<p>4.6 Where required (i.e., these are not available online anywhere), vocabularies and FAIR Implementation profiles registered, and time stamped in Research Vocabularies Australia (including outcomes of WP6)</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Negotiations begun with vocab owners - checking legal issues</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Currently RVA only stores vocabularies of controlled values, not metadata schemas or definitions of terms that only have numeric measurements, e.g., CF Conventions, MT_Metdata. Working with ARDC on a proposal to expand the capability of RVA. We are also looking at how the NERC Vocab server is publishing netCDF conventions.</p> <p>FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) drafted for each of the Geophysics 2030 collections via the FIP Wizard.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Controlled vocabularies included in the mt_metadata profile reviewed in preparation for addition to RVA. Unfortunately, these definitions of terms used to define the metadata terms used in MT and PS are still not allowed in RVA. ARDC will allow 2030 to place the profile of mt_metadata in the demonstration version of RVA. However, formal publication is awaiting a review of whether the scope of RVA will be expanded to take definitions and metadata-style vocabularies. If RVA decides not to expand its scope, then 2030 will need to look elsewhere for another vocabulary service that can publish our profile of mt_metadata, possibly an established community service such as the NERC Vocabulary Server.</p> <p>FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) published for each of the Geophysics 2030 collections via Zenodo. Links to the FIPs added to the NCI Data Catalogue records.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

<p>4.7 Milestone Report 2 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Delayed because the types of vocabs required by the project cannot be ingested into RVA currently as it only takes vocabularies with agreed values.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): UAT to be combined with WP#2.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>4.8 Second consultation with Stakeholder groups - AuScope project leaders, Industry, Federal and State Surveys</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Liaison continuing with AuScope project leaders, Industry, Federal and State Surveys.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Consultation continuing with AuScope project leaders and other key personnel within Australia and internationally. Formal permission to share mt_metadata profile via RVA obtained. Working with authors regarding formal publication of the latest/current profile.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>4.9 Second revision of data specification that is aligned with modern international research and HPC/D requirements, and can be supported under the existing tools under WP5</p>	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Research on International standards continuing with key groups internationally.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): NCI staff set-up as a RVA contributor. The mt_metadata standard and the AuScope AusLAMP profile have been published via RVA demo. A new W3ID domain has been set up for the mt_metadata standard. The vocabulary is only available in demo form and could not be published formally, as the ARDC Research Vocabularies Australia only hosts Vocabularies that have controlled values for each element. Unfortunately, the MT_metadata standard does not comply with this rule as it only has definitions of terms and the values that go with each term are mostly numeric.</p> <p>Completed as far as is possible.</p>	<p>Aug 2023</p>

4.10 Final Report contribution: including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR	Final Report (June 2023): UAT was completed. Testers verified access to the vocabularies available in RVA demo. Completed August 2023.	Aug 2023
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Work Package 5: Scalable computing and data analysis		
Deliverable Description	Progress details	Completed
5.1 First release of HPC data assimilation (e.g., Firedrake and associated adjoint code) used in ARDC Geodynamic ADjoint Optimization PlaTform Project led by Rhodri Davies (ANU) which is next-gen HPC case for AuScope's use of data.	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): The following Firedrake software enabled by Linux user environment modules are now available in project up99 : firedrake/20210827 firedrake/20210902 A tutorial on how to run Firedrake on Gadi can be found here .	Oct 2021
5.2 Prepare software and notebooks into the OOD framework and ready for use on Gadi	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Open source geophysics software and tutorials have been deployed in project up99: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/KAIWC Software has been tested on both NCI's Australian Research Environment (ARE) and Gadi . The retirement of the Open On Demand service is set to be completed on 30 June 2023. All work transferred to ARE.	Nov 2021
5.3 First quick survey of software used for processing the first candidate data, and establish the format for a larger future survey	Progress Report 1 (May 2022) A review of the software used for processing Musgraves MT time series data was conducted and appropriate software was installed on Gadi. The initial review was assuming time series data were going to be in a NetCDF format. However, the 2022 publication of the MTH5/mt_metadata international standard for MT time series (meta)data made it clear that we would need to update AuScope AusLAMP MT time series data in order to align with AusLAMP time series data produced by GA and time series data produced by the international community (e.g., the EarthScope USArray magnetotelluric program).	May 2022
5.4 Establish first set of software on NCI (ARE, Gadi) to be used for processing data, focused on MT	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Documentation on the MT software/ modules available on NCI (ARE, Gadi) and examples of how to use them can be found here .	Dec 2021
5.5 Survey of priority software that has been used by the various stakeholders / partners (all the aforementioned programs, but also including the Loop project and industry stakeholders) that could be used for MT and PS for the	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): First survey of potential geophysical software to install on Gadi/ARE is available here .	Apr 2022

<p>targeted first release of codes on NCI. The codes are to focus on 1) how to process the raw data to a higher-level product and 2) suitable for NCI's computing environments (Gadi and ARE)</p>		
<p>5.6 Establish first set of software on NCI (ARE, Gadi) to be used for processing data, focused on PS</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): The "NCI-geophysics" linux module under NCI project code up99 has been developed to allow for a more fluid user experience when undertaking geophysical data analysis and processing. The module integrates Python, Julia and R environments together with thousands of pre-built libraries. The current release of NCI-geophysics (22.04) includes the following geophysics/geoscience/data science software packages:</p> <p>Obspy: A Python framework for Seismology</p> <p>Pyrocko: An open source seismology toolbox and library written in Python.</p> <p>SimPEG: An open source Python package for simulation and gradient based parameter estimation in geophysical applications.</p> <p>MTpy: A Python toolbox for magnetotelluric (MT) Data Processing, Analysis, Modelling and Visualisation.</p> <p>MTH5: Package for reading/writing/manipulating MTH5 files.</p> <p>mt_metadata: A tool to standardise both time series and transfer function metadata for magnetotelluric data.</p> <p>HiQGA: a general purpose package for spatial statistical inference, geophysical forward modelling, Bayesian inference and inversion (both deterministic and probabilistic).</p> <p>JUDI: a framework for large-scale seismic modelling and inversion and designed to enable rapid translations of algorithms to fast and efficient code that scales to industry-size 3D problems.</p> <p>Oceananigans: a fast, friendly, flexible software package for finite volume simulations of the nonhydrostatic and hydrostatic Boussinesq equations on CPUs and GPUs.</p> <p>Intake: a lightweight set of tools for loading and sharing data in data science projects.</p> <p>Dask: a flexible library for parallel computing in Python.</p> <p>Xarray: a python package for working with labelled multi-dimensional (a.k.a. n-dimensional, ND) arrays.</p> <p>hvPlot: a familiar and high-level API for data exploration and visualisation.</p> <p>seaborn: a Python data visualisation library based on matplotlib. It provides a high-level interface for drawing attractive and informative statistical graphics.</p>	<p>June 2022</p>

	<p>geoscale: Geological Time Scale plotting package.</p> <p>CHNOSZ: an integrated set of tools for thermodynamic calculations in aqueous geochemistry and geobiochemistry.</p> <p>ETAS: Fits the space-time Epidemic Type Aftershock Sequence ('ETAS') model to earthquake catalogues using a stochastic 'declustering' approach.</p> <p>phreeqc: A geochemical modelling program developed by the US Geological Survey that is designed to perform a wide variety of aqueous geochemical calculations, including speciation, batch-reaction, one-dimensional reactive-transport, and inverse geochemical calculations.</p> <p>ggplot2: a system for declaratively creating graphics, based on The Grammar of Graphics.</p> <p>ggtern: An extension to ggplot2, for the creation of Ternary Diagrams.</p> <p>purrr: enhances R's functional programming (FP) toolkit by providing a complete and consistent set of tools for working with functions and vectors.</p> <p>furrr: combines purrr's family of mapping functions with future's parallel processing capabilities.</p> <p>plot3D: Functions for viewing 2-D and 3-D data, including perspective plots, slice plots, surface plots, scatter plots, etc.</p> <p>tseries: Time series analysis and computational finance.</p> <p>tidymodels: a collection of packages for modelling and machine learning using tidyverse principles.</p>	
<p>5.7 Milestone Report 1 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): The "NCI-geophysics" linux module and library of Jupyter notebooks has been generated and verified by independent NCI testers. However, it has not been released yet to users. The NCI-geophysics environment and other MT software will be showcased at the next Australian MT Practitioners Group meeting (end of June) or the proposed Workshop on "MT processing on HPC Frontiers".</p> <p>We believe that FAIR does not apply to this Milestone, because this milestone is about scalable computation and the agreed contractual FAIR output requirements for this project are for data, not for computation: see https://ardc.edu.au/about_us/policies-and-guidelines/fair-data-guidelines-for-project-data-outputs/</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Two versions of NCI-geophys (22.06 and 22.11) have been released to the geophysics community: See https://opus.nci.org.au/x/1wG7CQ .</p> <p>One positive tester report is already available. We have a broader set of testers in train as part of the AEGC workshop in March 2023.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Four versions of NCI-geophys (22.06, 22.11, 23.03, 23.04) have been released to the geophysics community. See https://opus.nci.org.au/x/1wG7CQ for more information.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

	<p>User Acceptance Tests (UATs) have been developed for the NCI-geophysics environment: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/yIPAD</p>	
<p>5.8 MT Data Only (30% of total data). First set of processing of raw data, associated data, and model data, that will process a dataset and then regenerate a quality-controlled dataset or a previous higher level (previously less resolution product), including supporting improved I and R in FAIR and WP4.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Total data comprises 30% MT. This work package item relates to this component only. Major delay to change in MT time series data standard. This will be resolvable once standard stabilises.</p> <p>A workshop is planned with the relevant international group developing the standard. The fall-back position will be that we use the current standard. Recent work is showing that you can get the data into the new standard but being able to do that depends on how consistently the current standard has been applied in existing data sets.</p> <p>Vertical integration is the goal, to be able to relate a derived product from the source data. Currently it's not even possible to relate any product back to its source dataset. With the Musgraves dataset, we will show how this can be done transparently, and publish the method through jupyter notebooks. Even if the fallback position - i.e. of using current time series practices for MT (not fully adopting the new standard) - the vertical integration or MT (i.e., the objective of the project) will be realised.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Had discussions with Jared Peacock of the USGS about the AURORA time series processing code (https://github.com/simpeg/aurora) which is based on Gary Egberts time series processing codes (http://www.mtnet.info/programs/egbert.html). The Musgraves time series dataset was processed with the BIRRP code of Chave & Thompson (https://www.who.edu/science/AOPE/people/achave/Site/Next1.html). Therefore, we asked Jared if it would be a good idea to adapt the BIRRP code to allow for MTH5 as input which he agreed was a good idea.</p> <p>Contributed tutorials to the MTH5 github repository on how to get from Earth Data Logger MT time series data (ASCII format) into MTH5/mt_metadata at scale for two MTH5 data models (all stations in a single MTH5 file and a single MTH5 file per station): https://github.com/kujaku11/mth5/blob/master/docs/examples/notebooks/mth5_in_parallel.ipynb https://github.com/kujaku11/mth5/blob/master/docs/examples/notebooks/mth5_in_parallel_one_file_per_station.ipynb</p> <p>Prepared BIRRP example in the mth5 format and adapted the BIRRP code to allow for mth5 files as input.</p> <p>Tested the updated BIRRP code on the example mth5 time series data and the updated code is working as expected. Next we need to develop code to automate bulk processing of MT time series data to frequency domain response functions. Following this, tutorials will be developed and demonstrated at the AEGC 2023 "Scaling MT acquisition, processing, interpretation, and people" workshop.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Meeting held on 9 December with the developers of TileDB for seismology and GNSS data. There appears to be a way forward.</p>	<p>Mar 2023</p>

	<p>Developed the MagnetoTellurics time series data publication v1 (MTtsdp_v1) codes: https://github.com/nci/MTtsdp/tree/master/MTtsdp_v1 .</p> <p>These codes were used to automate the generation of Level 0 and Level 1 MT time series products in the MTH5/mt_metadata format. See: https://github.com/nci/MTtsdp/blob/master/MTtsdp_v1/mth5_onefileperstation_mt_metadata_v0.2.2_level0.py</p> <p>https://github.com/nci/MTtsdp/blob/master/MTtsdp_v1/mth5_onefileperstation_mt_metadata_v0.2.2_level1.py</p> <p>Additionally, codes were developed to demonstrate running MT time series processing at scale for the Musgraves time series MTH5/mt_metadata dataset (https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/tzp3-td94, https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/tnez-h962, https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/akcy-n669) on the NCI Gadi supercomputer: https://github.com/nci/MTtsdp/blob/master/MTtsdp_v1/birrp_multiple_stations_multiple_runs_mt_metadata_v0.2.2.py</p>	
<p>5.9 Establish first Jupyter analysis notebooks that can make first use of NCI intake / STAC structures and interoperable with other domains</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Minor Delay with implementation of Stac Structures.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Work is still continuing on Intake/Stac structures. The methodology has been developed and tested on climate dataset examples.</p> <p>Geophysics examples will be added in the new year. The priority is to enable intake structures since the priority for the project is using in-situ technologies - as opposed to users only seeking download (which is the focus of STAC).</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Documentation on NCI data indexing can be found here: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/xgC9D</p> <p>An example notebook that utilises Intake on some example Geoscience Australia Geophysics Reference Data Collection data was developed: https://nbviewer.org/github/NCI-data-analysis-platform/geophysics/blob/main/geophysics_2030_UATs/Geophysics_data_indexing.ipynb</p>	<p>May 2023</p>
<p>5.10 Review of AI/ML codes that would be suitable for the AuScope PS and MT data, and data standards (e.g., "Fully AI ready")</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Delayed due to standard issues.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022) The review of AI/ML codes is under way and is on track for December 2022 completion. The aim is to test our AI/ML environments on the OpenFWI tutorials (https://openfwi-lanl.github.io/) which include datasets and benchmarks for machine learning driven Seismic Full Waveform Inversion (FWI).</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): A review of AI/ML codes was completed in December 2022: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/19ShqNoNvXQSiXVYZ9OP6pbycEc0Jaj001kHWYI8Bw-l/edit#slide=id.g1601ae85b7e_0_247</p>	<p>Dec 2022</p>

<p>5.11 Milestone Report 2 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022) Testers being organised. 2 Testers volunteered (one from ANU, for PS; one from CSIRO, for MT).</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): The following UATs were sent out to two users for testing and feedback: 1. Examples that demonstrate how to use the NCI-geophysics environment and NCI's data indexing infrastructure: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/vIPAD and https://nbviewer.org/github/NCI-data-analysis-platform/geophysics/tree/main/geophysics_2030_UATs/</p> <p>2. A geophysics related example that demonstrate how to use NCI's AI/ML environment: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/Q4FnDw</p> <p>The two testers came back with very positive reports about using these environments.</p>	<p>May 2023</p>
<p>5.12 Second major release of software on NCI (OOD, gadi) AI/ML to be used for both analysing and processing MT/PS data (including improved I and R in FAIR and WP4).</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): On track. https://opus.nci.org.au/x/eYAtC</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): The NCI AI/ML environment under NCI project code dk92 has been developed to allow Machine Learning analysis and processing by utilising Gadi GPU resources.</p> <p>The module contains popular machine learning packages including tensorflow-gpu and pytorch-gpu together with general purpose data processing packages such as xarray, dask and ray. One can utilise multiple GPU nodes to run Tensorflow or Pytorch based projects via parallelisation frameworks including Horovod and Ray.</p> <p>A geophysics related tutorial that uses the NCI AI/ML environment was developed. This tutorial demonstrates how to train and test an InversionNet model on an example dataset contained within the OpenFWI collection of large-scale, multi-structural benchmark datasets for machine learning driven seismic Full Waveform Inversion. The tutorial can be found here: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/Q4FnDw</p>	<p>Apr 2023</p>
<p>5.13 Final Report contribution: including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Seeking testers.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): The following UATs were sent out to two users for testing and feedback: 1. examples that demonstrate how to use the NCI-geophysics environment and NCI's data indexing infrastructure: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/vIPAD and https://nbviewer.org/github/NCI-data-analysis-platform/geophysics/tree/main/geophysics_2030_UATs/</p>	<p>May 2023</p>

	<p>2. a geophysics related example that demonstrate how to use NCI's AI/ML environment: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/Q4FnDw</p> <p>The two testers came back with very positive reports about using these environments.</p>	
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Work Package 6: Dirt-to-Desktop FAIR profiles for future acquisitions		
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Deliverable Description	Progress details	Completed
<p>6.1 First draft of FAIR profiles for Dirt-to-desktop requirements compliant with current international standards, including coordination with ARDC-funded FAIMS recommendations (Field Acquired Information Management System - https://ardc.edu.au/project/faims-3-0-electronic-field-notebooks/) due in early 2022</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): There have been delays in the FAIMS project. The instability of both MT and PS data standards also contributed to this delay.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Attributes for PS sorted out and sent to FAIMS. For MT, we will use the attributes that are being developed in the US.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Passive Seismic demo workbook published by FAIMS staff to GitHub. Set of field attributes defined for field collection.</p> <p>Completed November June 2023</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>6.2 Milestone Report 1 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): UAT not applicable and See Section 8 for FAIR.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): UAT will be reported for whole of project.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Completed: UAT Reported elsewhere</p> <p>Completed June 2023.</p>	<p>June 2023</p>
<p>6.3 Second draft of FAIR profiles for Dirt-to-desktop, considering results from WP1-5</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Underway</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022): PS profile defined, MT one will be based on MT AusLAMP legacy data. Project is using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) as a machine actionable declaration of all standards and protocols 16 FAIR principles.</p> <p>Completed October 2022.</p>	<p>Oct 2022</p>
<p>6.4 Milestone Report 2 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not yet Started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022) Awaiting testers when package is complete</p>	<p>June 2023</p>

	Final Report (June 2023): Limited testing done because users are investigating a commercial solution for PS and the MT champion for FAIMS left their organisation so we had no testers. <i>Completed as far as possible.</i>	
6.5 Third draft of FAIR profiles for Dirt-to-desktop, considering results from WP1-5	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started. Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Work continuing. Final Report (June 2023): Profiles as defined in 6.3 could not be improved. <i>Completed as far as possible.</i>	June 2023
6.6 Release candidate profile that could be used in Dirt-to-desktop processing.	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started. Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Work continuing. Final Report (June 2023): MT Profile released, based on MT Legacy profile: yet to be tested. <i>Completed as far as possible.</i>	June 2023
6.7 Final Report contribution: including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not Started. Progress Report 2 (November 2022): Work continuing. Final Report (June 2023): Having difficulty finding testers for FAIMS profile. <i>Completed as far as possible.</i>	June 2023

Work Package 7 - Measuring Impact		
Deliverable Description	Progress details	Completed
7.1 Researching and plan how to approach/apply COUNTER	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Plan completed regarding COUNTER RD and NCI's reporting and impact workflows. <i>Completed April 2022.</i>	Apr 2022
7.2 Milestone Report 1 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR	Progress Report 1 (May 2022): UAT not applicable. <i>Completed April 2023.</i>	Apr 2022

<p>7.3 Implement the COUNTER Code of Practice for Research Data in Repositories for NCI data services.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): On track.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022) The trial implementation of COUNTER is underway. Following actions are completed: - Mock COUNTER reports prepared (csv format); - NCI THREDDS Data Service web logs obtained; - Map log entries to COUNTER metadata elements; and - COUNTER-processor reporting software installed and configured.</p> <p>The following tasks are currently in progress: - COUNTER reports for sample THREDDS data collection prepared (JSON format); and - NCI COUNTER Report (in draft).</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): The COUNTER RD report was finalised following consultation with stakeholders including ARDC, DataCite and Laure Haak. The COUNTER RD report published on Zenodo under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence, in accordance with FAIR principles.</p> <p>NCI Australia. (2023). COUNTER Usage Metrics: National Computational Infrastructure - ARDC Project Report (1.0). NCI Australia. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8093111</p> <p>Completed July 2023.</p>	<p>July 2023</p>
<p>7.4 Milestone Report 2 contribution, including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022) Organising testers.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): Consultation/feedback sought from various internal and external stakeholders/experts as part of the testing/assessment process.</p> <p>Completed July 2023.</p>	<p>July 2023</p>
<p>7.5 Integration of persistent identifiers, where provided by the data suppliers, into the monitoring and usage of NCI data collections to support tracking and monitoring of research outcomes and impact of the repository.</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022) Decision made on identifiers that are possible.</p> <p>Final Report (June 2023): DOIs were used to match/track usage in the COUNTER RD trial implementation. Project team is monitoring developments in the integration of persistent identifiers and applications for research outcomes tracking/monitoring. Team is an active member of the RDA Complex Citations Working Group.</p> <p>Completed as far as possible.</p>	<p>July 2023</p>
<p>7.6 Requirements document for enhancements to the NCI user registration model that would enable capturing information</p>	<p>Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not started.</p> <p>Progress Report 2 (November 2022) On track.</p>	<p>July 2023</p>

<p>about funding, intended use cases, and cross-reference against HPC projects of data users at NCI.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Final Report (June 2023):</p> <p>Final <u>COUNTER report</u> includes recommended future developments to help guide short/longer term planning exercises and ensure that infrastructure is designed to capture/store/share usage metrics in future. The report includes some suggestions regarding tracking of HPC usage and information about usage/consumption tracking at NCI. Discussion regarding funding identifiers and tracking discussed in WP#3.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Completed July 2023.</p>	
<p>7.7 Research and plan how NCI can track the research usage through publications and grants associated with the NCI data collections.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Progress Report 1 (May 2022): Not started.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Progress Report 2 (November 2022) On track.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Final Report (June 2023):</p> <p>1) See WP#3 for detailed analysis of the tracking of research usage via publications/citations and grant identifiers. 2) Monitoring plan developed with Laure Haak.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Completed July 2023</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">July 2023</p>
<p>7.8 Final Report contribution: including User Acceptance Testing (UAT) and FAIR</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Progress Report 1 (May 2022):</p> <p>When finalised, the COUNTER implementation report is planned for release under a Creative Commons Licence and to be assigned a DOI.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Progress Report 2 (November 2022) On track.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Final Report (June 2023):</p> <p>Following stakeholder consultation and review, the outputs for WP#7 have been published and shared. Monitoring framework developed by Laure Haak to be used for post-project reporting at 12 and 24 months.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Completed July 2023.</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">July 2023</p>

2.2 Project outputs

Key outputs of the Geophysics 2030 project included the curation and release of the [national geophysics collections](#), development of the software environments for [AI/ML](#) and [Geophysics](#), delivery of outreach and training (see Section 2.3) and production of various publications and associated project resources (see Section 5.1).

The following reports against the individual outputs as listed in the Project Plan.

Output 1: Create first exemplar cases and plan for rawer forms of the AuScope funded MT and PS datasets to be accessible at the NCI facility following standardised data processing and connected to derivative products through identifiers.

The following high-resolution Geophysics 2030 Collections were released on HPC environments:

- a) AuScope (2023): AuScope Magnetotellurics (MT) Collection. v1. NCI Australia.dataset. <https://doi.org/10.25914/mtjg-jp22>
- b) AuScope; Research School of Earth Sciences (RSES), Australian National University (2023): AuScope Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) Collection. v1. NCI Australia.dataset. <https://doi.org/10.25914/zr9f-1e98>
- c) Cudahy, T. et. al. (2023): National ASTER Map of Australia. v1. NCI Australia.dataset. <https://doi.org/10.25914/5f224f36ec890>
- d) Research School of Earth Sciences (RSES), The Australian National University (2023): AusPass Passive Seismic Collection. NCI Australia.dataset. <https://doi.org/10.25914/zyay-2g34>

The AuScope/NCI MT dataset was used as a pathfinder on how to move other minimally processed, high-resolution geophysics datasets into the NCI Data Collection and create an integrated national high-resolution reference collection of other geophysical types (magnetic, gravity, AEM, radiometrics, INSAR, GRACE). Figure 1 shows some of the different types of geophysical data collected in Australia, the physical property measured and the typical depths of investigation of each geophysical technique.

Figure 1: Types of geophysical data collected in Australia, the physical property measured and the depth of the Earth that is sampled: also shown is the depth of current mining. Figure modified from original version from Richard Chopping (GSWA).

Catalogue metadata has been structured to enable ‘vertical’ integration between repositories. Datasets were documented according to the level of processing (e.g., from the packed raw time series archive to the Level 0 and Level 1 time series products to the Level 2 time series processed transfer function products). Individual collections and datasets were each assigned DOIs as identifiers; these were then used to reference the source data in the lineage statements of higher-level outputs.

Update frequency	As needed
Format	MTH5 / mt_metadata
Lineage	<p>This dataset was derived from a raw source dataset first published by the University of Adelaide (Heinson, G. 2022).</p> <p>The MagnetoTellurics time series data publication (MTtsdp) codes (Rees, N. et al. 2023) were used to create the Level 1 concatenated, resampled, rotated MTH5/MT_metadata time series data products. The Level 0 concatenated MTH5/MT_metadata time series data products (https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/9y8g-9x90) were used as input for the generation of the Level 1 concatenated, resampled, rotated MTH5/MT_metadata time series data products.</p> <p>References: Heinson, G. (2022). Magnetotelluric surveys of the AusLAMP Musgraves Province within Western Australia, 2016 to 2018 (packed raw time series data) [Data set]. NCI Australia. https://doi.org/10.25914/AJ1K-FJ69 Rees, N., Wang, S., Conway, D. et. al. (2023). nci/MTtsdp: MTtsdp_v1.0.0 (v1.0.0) [Software]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7707364</p>

Figure 2: Lineage example from a [sample geophysical dataset](#) in the NCI Data Catalogue.

In addition, external data portals hosting higher-level products are now starting to reference the rawer data available via the NCI Data Catalogue. For example, the Geological Survey of Western Australia vertically integrated the [AusLAMP Musgraves Magnetotelluric Level 2 EDI files](#) hosted on their local MAGIX portal with the Level 0 and Level 1 time series data hosted at NCI.

Output 2: In collaboration with other collectors of MT and PS data, FAIR implementation profiles will be developed for each major data types to enable harmonisation of data from multiple surveys not just nationally, but to enable interoperation of national datasets with major international research data collections and to meet compliance with journal submission policies.

A FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) documents the implementation choices for each of the [FAIR Principles](#). FIPs have the potential to accelerate interoperability of geophysical and geochemical datasets acquired by different communities/repositories and at scale. By providing more specificity than existing FAIR assessment methodologies and most metadata schemas, they build toward machine-interoperability.

The Geophysics 2030 FIPs were prepared via the [FIP Wizard](#) and are available in different human-readable and machine-actionable formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, PDF). Individual FIPs were created for each of the Geophysics 2030 collections as well as for the [NCI Data Catalogue](#). DOIs were minted for each of the FIPs via Zenodo; they were then linked to the relevant catalogue records for the collection (and are referenced as part of the ISO 19115 metadata and visible via the GUI). To provide machine-readable data documentation, the [mt metadata standard](#) and the [AuScope AusLAMP profile](#) were both added to Research Vocabularies Australia (RVA) demo environment.

The published FIPs include:

- NCI Data Catalogue: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8030958>
- AuScope Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) Collection: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185343>
- AusPass Passive Seismic Collection: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185347>
- National ASTER Map of Australia: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185345>
- AuScope Magnetotellurics (MT) Collection: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185349>

As part of the project, NCI Australia investigated and trialled the implementation of standardised research data usage metrics. NCI's THREDDS data service was used as a case study for the implementation of the [COUNTER Code of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics](#) (COUNTER RD) usage statistics. The [COUNTER Processor](#) application was installed and used to process the THREDDS web log files and generate sample reports for selected Geophysics 2030 datasets. The '[COUNTER Usage Metrics: National Computational Infrastructure - ARDC Project Report \(1.0\)](#)' (2023) evaluated the ability of COUNTER RD to capture usage in an HPC facility and identified a number of new internal development priorities for NCI.

Output 3: Better recording of lineages between calibration and interconnection of hyperspectral data collections in Australia (such as TERN calibration datasets, and other AuScope projects).

Data repository coordination is key to supporting horizontal integration of geophysical data releases. Leveraging disciplinary metadata standards supports integration of multiple datasets from disparate data providers.

An example of horizontal integration is demonstrated in Figure 3, where the NCI hosted Ferric Oxide Composition layer of the [National ASTER Map of Australia](#) is plotted alongside the locations of [34 OzFlux Towers](#) that are hosted on the [TERN THREDDS Data Server](#). The example includes time series data (CO₂ and absolute humidity) recorded at six OzFlux towers maintained by TERN. These flux towers have been continuously recording measurements of the exchange of energy and mass between the surface and the atmosphere made at many locations around Australia since 2001. In addition to the fluxes of momentum, heat, water vapour and carbon dioxide, there is supporting meteorological data such as incoming and outgoing radiation, air temperature, humidity, wind speed and direction, soil temperature, soil moisture and precipitation which can be used for calibration of other datasets collected remotely via satellite. Please see the [OzFlux Variable Names and Definitions document](#) for a full list of variable names organised by [OzFlux Processing Level](#).

The OzFlux data can be accessed directly via OpenDAP web services hosted on the [TERN THREDDS Data Server](#) and there was no need to store the data locally at NCI. For horizontal integration purposes, if the date of the hyperspectral remote sensed images are known, it is possible to select the precise observational measurement data from the OZ flux dataset at exactly the same time. An [accompanying Jupyter Notebook tutorial](#) has been

developed demonstrating horizontal integration between software using NCI's gdata file system and TERN's THREDDS Data Server.

Figure 3: OzFlux tower site locations (red dots) are plotted on the ASTER Ferric Oxide Composition of Australia layer. Time series data for CO₂ and absolute humidity are shown for six OzFlux tower sites. ASTER data were sourced from [NCI's Gadi gdata file system](#) and the OzFlux data were drawn from the [TERN THREDDS Data Server](#).

Technically, this horizontal integration of data from two separate repositories could be achieved, because the data accessed via web services was very small in volume. There will be a limit to doing this with large volume datasets and in some cases, the data may need to be moved and stored locally.

Output 4: Computational model data through data assimilation, SAM programs or by applying AI/ML techniques.

Science in all disciplines now require more specialised environments for managing workflows and analysing data. NCI has enabled a number of these environments for both interactive and computationally intensive use - which is supported via Virtual Desktop Infrastructures (scientific desktops), JupyterLab, and via the command line or batch systems. These environments are in addition to the various software libraries installed under /apps on Gadi and

also accessible through the Australian Research Environment (ARE) interface. The [Specialised Environments Home](#) details the different flavours of specialised environments that are available at NCI. The Geophysics 2030 project worked on creating software environments more tuned to geophysical use cases whilst maintaining cross domain integration.

To allow for a more fluid experience in geophysical data analysis and processing, the [NCI-geophysics module](#) was developed which integrates Python, Julia and R environments together with thousands of pre-built libraries. NCI users can access these libraries directly and use them within their own workflows without having to spend significant time building their own software environments. One advantage of having a shared, quality controlled, community driven, regularly updated geophysical software environment module is that scientific workflows can easily be shared and reproduced without geophysical researchers having to grapple with software engineering principles such as containerisation, package dependencies, package managers, compiling for HPC architectures, debugging, PATH variables, etc. With the NCI-geophysics module, it is as simple as running:

```
$ module use /g/data/up99/modulefiles
```

```
$ module load NCI-geophys
```

and any user has access to over 1500 Python/Julia/R libraries that can be used either on Gadi or via a JupyterLab or via a full Virtual Desktop (VDI) on the ARE.

To simplify the use of AI/ML tools on HPC, NCI developed and continues to manage an [AI/ML environment](#) that allows researchers to more easily run their AI/ML workflows using multiple GPU nodes on Gadi. This module has bundled together many of the major data science and machine learning packages including [Tensorflow](#), [Pytorch](#), [Scikit-learn](#), [Horovod](#), [Xarray](#), [Dask](#) and [Ray](#).

In addition to the NCI geophysics and AI/ML modules, standalone open source geophysics related applications that support parallel computation have progressively been added to Gadi including [OpenQuake](#), [ModEM](#), [esys-escript](#), [Mare2DEM](#), [Firedrake](#), [FEMTIC](#) and [BIRRP](#). The [Geophysics Specialised Environments](#) page lists the geophysical software that is currently available at NCI.

These tools and environments grant geophysicists the capability to more easily and more rapidly run their processing, analysis, modelling or AI/ML workflows on HPC.

Output 5: Create data publication and citation workflow that is modernised to address current international standards and use of identifiers.

International standard identifiers are key in supporting accurate data citation and reproducibility. They also have a pivotal role in disambiguating the people and organisations involved in the funding, acquisition, processing, and publication of data.

Globally Unique Persistent Resolvable Identifiers (GUPRIs) have been assigned to all the Geophysics 2030 datasets and collections. In the [NCI Data Catalogue](#), all the Geophysics 2030 records have had a [Digital Object Identifier](#) (DOI) minted via [DataCite](#). The DOI is visible on the catalogue landing page for each dataset (and in a machine-readable format in the ISO 19115 metadata). Each version of the data has a unique identifier to enable citation and scientific reproducibility.

The [NCI Data Catalogue](#) schema captures information about the people and organisations involved in the data acquisition, funding, processing and publication. A range of different roles can be represented, from funder and author to publisher and contributor. This information is crucial to support attribution and citation of the data. Implementation of persistent identifiers for people and organisations supports interoperability between systems and services. For the Geophysics 2030 records, person and organisation identifiers have been captured and stored in the database. [ORCIDs](#) and [RORs](#) are also included in the ISO 19115 metadata in a machine-readable format to facilitate interoperability.

The [NCI Data Catalogue](#) records capture various elements relating to funding relationships. Where relevant, detailed credit statements have been added to the ISO 19115 metadata. These statements allow custom acknowledgements to be inserted in a human-readable format. Where available, grant identifiers have been included. The format of the grant identifier is variable depending on the funding institution. DOIs and other Globally Unique Persistent Identifiers (GUPRIs) are preferred.

Acknowledgements

The Geophysics 2030 project received co-investment from AuScope and the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) to support the data curation at the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI Australia) (<https://doi.org/10.47486/XN002>). AuScope, the ARDC and NCI Australia are enabled by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS).

Figure 4: Acknowledgement statement from a sample catalogue record

An [international geophysical standards review](#) was undertaken to determine international community-preferred standards for raw and derivative datasets in various geophysical domains. For MT, much of the international and Australian community are beginning to move towards the [MTH5/mt_metadata](#) time series data and metadata standard. With that in mind, [the MagnetoTellurics time series data publication v1 \(MTtsdp_v1\)](#) codes were developed and used to automate the generation of the [Level 0 and Level 1 MT time series products](#) into the international MTH5/mt_metadata standard.

Codes were also developed to [demonstrate running MT time series processing at scale](#) on the NCI Gadi supercomputer. Table 1 shows some benchmarking that was done to generate the MTH5/mt_metadata products and associated transfer functions (EDI files) for entire MT surveys in parallel. Creating parallelised workflows that can be distributed over HPC clusters can greatly reduce the time to process MT data, and geophysical data in general.

Table 1: Benchmark tests for generating different MT time series processing levels in the MTH5/mt_metadata standard using both the [NCI Geophysics environment](#) and [the MagnetoTellurics time series data publication v1 \(MTtsdp_v1\)](#) codes. A benchmark for running MT time series processing using an MTH5 adapted version of the

[Bounded Influence Remote Reference Processing code](#) over an entire survey in parallel to generate one EDI file per station was also conducted.

Dataset of 93 MT stations	Serial I/O	MPI based Parallel I/O (96 cores)
Level 0: one MTH5/mt_metadata file for all stations	~ 14 hours	~ 35 minutes
Level 0: one MTH5/mt_metadata file per station	~ 5 hours 47 minutes	~ 4 minutes
Level 1: one MTH5/mt_metadata file per station	~ 49 minutes	~ 1.2 minutes
Level 2: one EDI file per station	~ 2 hours 30 minutes	~ 2 minutes

One important point to note was that the Level 0 and Level 1 field metadata was originally not collected using the mt_metadata standard, and a significant effort went into developing translators to convert each original metadata element to the mt_metadata standard. As it turned out, only a fraction of the full mt_metadata standard was collected for the legacy AusLAMP MT datasets. Ideally, the full mt_metadata standard would be born digital on collection in the field as part of a dirt-to-desktop workflow.

2.3 Outreach and training activities

The following describes outreach and training activities that were undertaken with the data assets.

ACTIVITY	ACTIVITY DESCRIPTION	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS	DATE OF ACTIVITY
Webinar on Meeting Publisher Requirements: Data, Samples, Software, Models and Notebooks	This webinar discussed: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What researchers and those supporting research need to know about publisher requirements for FAIR data, samples, software, models and notebooks. 2. What are the pain points for researchers in meeting these requirements? Do researchers have access to the tools, repositories and the 	~60	23 November 2021

	<p>information they need to meet with the publisher/funder requirements?</p> <p>See https://youtu.be/HIWI21TJ27A</p>		
<p>Workshop on MT Data at the Frontiers of HPC</p>	<p>AuScope hosted an online workshop on ‘MT at the frontiers of HPC’ on Tuesday 25th October. The workshop aimed to develop a community understanding of Magnetotelluric research activities and plan for data, computing and software needs and accessibility in the future.</p> <p>MT researchers from both government agencies and universities presented their latest research enabled by HPC followed by staff from the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) and AuScope showcasing the community processing environments, tools, compute and storage available at NCI. The workshop concluded with a community discussion on the future computing and storage needs of MT researchers.</p> <p>Workshop details: https://www.eventbrite.com.au/e/mt-at-the-frontiers-of-hpc-tickets-441413849707</p> <p>Workshop presentations: https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1r6vQkXIFZiYcGA8y40mGJ3Lc09KbvLPa</p>	~ 46	25 October 2022
<p>AEGC 2023 workshop: Scaling MT acquisition, processing, interpretation and people (AuScope)</p>	<p>This workshop aimed to familiarise attendees from industry, research and government with the current capabilities for processing and modelling of magnetotelluric data on NCI’s high performance computing infrastructure. It also facilitated discussion on the current and future state of MT data in Australia (particularly the less processed forms) and included acquisition, software, computing and people as well as data.</p> <p>Workshop presentations: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1oCG8dURrAkgTcm-1We9pGaQIYyKjs0N?usp=</p>	31	13 March 2023

	sharing		
AuScope Special Seminar with ChEESE Program Leader Prof Arnau Folch	Arnau Folch, program leader of the EU Centre of Excellence for Exascale in Solid Earth (ChEESE) and Professor at Geosciences Barcelona (GEO3BCN-CSIC) presented this webinar to raise awareness of HPC initiatives in geophysics in Europe through the ChEESE project which develops translational research capabilities to the Exascale in geophysics, enabling multiscale, multiphysics and multi-hazard analysis.	70	6 February 2023
Developing a Next Generation Platform for Geodetic, Seismological and Other Geophysical Data Sets and Services	<p>The Data Services of IRIS and the Geodetic Data Services of UNAVCO have been supporting the seismological and geodetic research communities for many decades. Recently IRIS and UNAVCO established a project to design, develop and implement a common, cloud-based platform which will provide services for data queries across the internal repositories. This is similar to what we were establishing with the 2030 Geophysics project and the two projects compared infrastructures with a view to being able to interoperate between the two.</p> <p>Presentations: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1FGO67ZU_AQeqU8oAcYKgI9Qn-BckdmAW/view?usp=sharing</p> <p>Wyborn, L., Rees, N., Evans, B., Farrington, R. and Rawling, T. 2023. 2030 Geophysics Collection Project: Building A Geophysical Platform for Next Generation Computing. https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1jSe_i9e10Tw5InXWx_M0nddedPpZ3u72/edit#slide=id.p1</p>	16	23-27 May 2022

3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

The Geophysics 2030 project fits within a broader set of geophysics collaborations which include organisations such as NCI, AuScope, Geoscience Australia and CSIRO. Work to collect and release new high-resolution datasets of value to research, government and industry is continuing. Providing access to rawer forms of the data and promoting new standards and technology provides a model for other organisations and projects in the geosciences. Ultimately, through wider uptake of these next-generation standards for rawer data in industry it will be possible to incorporate/link to industry funded datasets hosted by the State/Territory Surveys, and industry will be able to seamlessly merge their private datasets.

AuScope will sustain funding to this infrastructure to ensure ongoing access to the datasets generated during this project and will build elements of its future “Downward Looking Telescope” infrastructure and data assimilation programs utilising it through the AuScope Simulation Assimilation and Modelling (SAM) team. AuScope, along with its collaborators, will commit to continue to maintain the existing infrastructure whilst there is funding available. TERN plans to sustain its references to their datasets under their standard services, which will support horizontal integration with the Geophysics 2030 outputs.

NCI will manage the community software including notebooks under its Software and Data Modernisation team, and maintain the quality of the datasets, and catalogue management within the Data Management team. These include arrangements for access, storing data assets and services. Software developed through the project has been shared via GitHub and will be upgraded/maintained as required by the community.

NCI had pre-aligned this project proposal with its strategic goals on uplifting staff in this area. While the project was to use this project to target the staff, the staff recruited will be more generally used for broader work rather than staying focused on uplifting geophysics. They have been therefore absorbed into its ongoing operational budget. While not necessarily dedicated to the ongoing activity, their skills are being maintained.

4 FAIR

4.1 Implementation of FAIR Data Guidelines

The following describes the project’s progress in making the project data outputs FAIR against the actions in the [ARDC FAIR Data Guidelines for Project Data Outputs](#).

FAIR Data Actions

#	FAIR ACTION	DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION
1	All data outputs are assigned appropriate PIDs, preferably a DOI	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs have been assigned DOIs.
2	All data outputs have metadata to enable discovery	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs have human and machine-readable metadata in the NCI Data Catalogue .
3	All data outputs have a record in Research Data Australia	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs were harvested to RDA (see NCI Contributor page).
4	All data outputs are registered with relevant discipline-specific discovery aggregators (if they exist)	NA
5	The persistent identifier for the data output being described is included in the metadata	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs have a DOI listed in the metadata.
6	All data outputs are made as openly available as possible; they are only closed where necessary	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs are made available under an open licence. Some data may be subject to temporary embargo.
7	All data outputs are made available through a repository	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs are stored on the NCI Gadi supercomputer, listed in the NCI Data Catalogue and available via the THREDDS Data Service .
8	All data outputs are available as a download and/or accessible through an open, documented API (where data is not closed).	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs are available via the THREDDS Data Service (where files are programmatically accessible and/or able to be individually downloaded).
9	If the data outputs are not openly available, there is a clear description on the landing page on how to request access to the data outputs and the conditions that need to be met.	The DAS collection is temporarily embargoed. NCI Data Catalogue metadata includes information about the embargo as well as a link to MyNCI/Mancini (for access requests).
10	The persistent identifier for the data output points to a landing page about the data output, even if the data output is not public (open).	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs have DOIs that resolve to records on the NCI Data Catalogue .
11	If the data output is not openly available there is an authorisation and authentication procedure to provide access to the data.	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs are openly accessible. NCI also has documented procedures for Gadi/HPC access.
12	The persistent identifier for the data output continues to point to a landing page, even if the data output is no longer available, and there is a policy to maintain these landing pages.	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs have a DOI which points to a landing page on the NCI Data Catalogue . NCI Data Collections team internal procedures for decommissioning data include maintaining 'tombstone' landing pages. Further information is available as part of the FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs).
13	Data outputs use community-agreed standard data formats (where such agreed formats exist).	Geophysics 2030 data outputs use relevant community data formats (e.g. netCDF, miniseed, HDF5, MTH5/mt_metadata etc.).

14	Metadata for the data output uses community-agreed standards (where such agreed standards exist).	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs use a standard metadata format (ISO 19115:2003); Planned GeoNetwork upgrade underway to migrate to ISO 19115-1:2014.
15	Data and metadata use community-agreed vocabularies, data models and ontologies (preferably internationally agreed ones where they exist).	<p>NCI Data Catalogue uses some community-agreed vocabularies (e.g. ANZSRC-2008-FOR, ISO 19115-1 topicCategory). Updates are planned as part of the GeoNetwork upgrade.</p> <p>Geophysics 2030 metadata records use a disciplinary-specific controlled vocabulary for granule data format (GCMD-GDF). NCI's request to add EDI and MTH5 formats was accepted by the GCMD community.</p> <p>The mt metadata standard and the AuScope AusLAMP profile have been made accessible via RVA demo. They could not be published formally as the ARDC Research Vocabularies Australia only hosts Vocabularies that have controlled values for each element. Unfortunately, the MT_metadata standard is for describing definitions of terms, but the values are mostly numeric: this type of vocabulary is currently not accepted by RVA.</p>
16	Metadata contains persistent identifiers for research objects and entities (people, organisations) linked to the data outputs (including ORCIDs, grantIDs, RAIDs, DOIs, IGSNs).	<p>All the Geophysics 2030 records have ORCIDs and RORs recorded via DataCite.</p> <p>Persistent identifiers such as ORCIDs, ARDC grantIDs and RORs are being captured in NCI systems and available in the NCI Data Catalogue metadata. Note we were not able to do Grant IDs yet for NCI and AuScope funding as these are awaiting the results of the trial of DataCite minting DOIs.</p>
17	All data outputs are assigned a machine readable licence (preferably CC-BY 4.0).	<p>Most Geophysics 2030 data outputs are licensed under CC-BY 4.0. A small number of legacy datasets are under similar licences (e.g CC-BY 3.0 (GSSA and MRT)).</p> <p>Changes have been made to ensure that all Geophysics 2030 metadata has the licence name/URL stored in separate fields to improve machine-readability (and in preparation for GeoNetwork/metadata upgrade).</p>
18	The licence information is available in a machine readable form on the landing page that the persistent identifier (for the data output) references.	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs list the licence on the landing page (in the HTML and XML).
19	There is a citation statement for the data output on the landing page that the persistent identifier references.	All Geophysics 2030 data outputs have formatted citations displaying in RDA and DataCite. All Geophysics 2030 collections records display a suggested citation in the NCI Data Catalogue.

		Plans to generate and display formatted citations in the upgraded GeoNetwork.
20	Provenance information on the data output is attached alongside the data.	Where relevant, provenance information is recorded in the metadata (see ISO 19115 LI Lineage).
21	Relevant discipline-specific metadata to enable reuse is captured and presented alongside the data output following research community best practice.	Geophysics 2030 data outputs record discipline-specific metadata to support reuse (e.g. netCDF metadata header information etc.).

5 PROJECT IMPACT

5.1 Communications and Engagement

The following table details of engagement with the community or stakeholders over the life of the project including: user community outreach, engagement or training activities undertaken; communication, promotional or editorial activities undertaken, including website pages, social media activity, media releases, articles, video content, etc; publications or published articles that mention the project or the data asset.

ACTIVITY	DETAILS	LINK TO MATERIALS
Web Page: 2030 Collections Project	Web page summary of project	https://ardc.edu.au/project/2030-geophysics-collections/
Web Page: Geophysics Data at NCI	Web page access to information about the geophysical data collections available at NCI.	https://opus.nci.org.au/x/dgC_Bg
Web Page: Geophysics Specialised Environments and Software at NCI	Web page access to information and examples regarding the geophysics specialised environments and software available at NCI.	https://opus.nci.org.au/x/KAIWC
Web Page: NCI Geophysics Community Space	Home web page for information about Geophysics happenings at the NCI.	https://opus.nci.org.au/x/bwC_Bg
Web Page: Geophysics 2030 Collections work packages	Web page summarising the various work packages undertaken during the 2030 Geophysics Collections project.	https://opus.nci.org.au/x/eQBvC
Poster presentation at the ESIP January 2022 Meeting, Virtual.	Wyborn, L., Rees, N., Evans, B., Rawling, T., Druken, K. and Klump, J., 2022. 2030 Geophysics HPC Collection Project: enabling vertical integration of successive	Presentation: https://figshare.com/articles/poster/2030_Geophysics_HPC_Collection_Project_enabling_vertical_integration_of_su

	<p>processing levels across multiple scales and sites. ESIP. Poster. https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.18318824.v1</p>	<p>ccessive_processing_levels_across_multiple_scales_and_sites/18318824</p>
<p>Poster presentation at the ESIP January 2022 Meeting, Virtual.</p>	<p>Rees, N., Yang, R., Sun, Y., Farrington, R., Evans, B., and Wyborn, L., 2023. Enabling Scalable Insitu Geophysical Data Analysis on the NCI HPC platform. ESIP. Poster. https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21919584.v1</p>	<p>Presentation: https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21919584.v1</p>
<p>Oral Presentation at the EGU General Assembly, May 2022.</p>	<p>Wyborn, L., Rees, N., Klump, J., Evans, B., Rawling, T., and Druken, K.: The Known Knowns, the Known Unknowns and the Unknown Unknowns of Geophysics Data Processing in 2030 , EGU General Assembly 2022, Vienna, Austria, 23–27 May 2022, EGU22-11012, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu22-11012</p>	<p>Abstract: https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU22/EGU22-11012.html Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1S2FNMbzSZ7P2Cj0oLQnVUISbndXyAfpK/edit#slide=id.p9</p>
<p>Poster at <u>ESIP January 2023 Meeting on Opening Doors to Open Science</u></p>	<p>Wyborn, L., Rees, N., Farrington, R., Dekker, A. G., 2023. In the Year of Open-source Science, Which Levels of Data Processing Should We Persist and Make FAIR?. ESIP. Poster. https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21937514.v1</p>	<p>Abstract: https://docs.google.com/document/d/16MNgVlx3US_cGMOT-lrTfhi21JfIfkUf2HuF42Onug/edit Presentation: https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.21937514.v1</p>
<p>Paper presented at <u>AEGC 2023</u> (March 2023).</p>	<p>Rees, N., Wyborn, L., Evans, B., Farrington, R., Rawling, T., Yang, R. and Sun, Y., 2023. Building a National High-Resolution Geophysics Reference Collection for 2030 Computation. Australian Society of Exploration Geophysicists Extended Abstracts, Volume 2023, 4th Australasian Exploration Geoscience Conference, Brisbane, 2023. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980192</p>	<p>Extended abstract: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7980192 Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1vx3eu3FsjG0XJvkqrYoirudFifUbBfCpaV4E-yH8OBRs/edit?usp=sharing</p>
<p>EGU General Assembly 2023, oral paper</p>	<p>Wyborn, L., Rees, N., Klump, J., Evans, B., Farrington, R., and Rawling, T.: Who Done It? Reproducibility of Data Products Also Requires Lineage to Determine Impact and Give Credit Where Credit is Due., EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-12864,</p>	<p>Abstract: https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-12864 Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1kikuQ3Ehhhg_8XEVYaFj2RDKKUsXo</p>

	https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-12864	KSk/edit#slide=id.p2
EGU General Assembly 2023, Town Hall	Complex Citations: Current Work to Ensure Proper Credit for 100+-cited Data and Software Objects	Program: https://meetingorganizer.copernicus.org/EGU23/sessionprogramme/4917
Webinar (April 2023) for the Australian Society of Exploration Geophysicists	Wyborn, L., 2023: Using 2030 Computational Techniques to Unleash the Untapped Potential of Existing Geophysical Datasets in Mineral Exploration: Opportunities and Challenges	Abstract: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UeNfJQwwrZIBNItWNDHygTTnM-5Znyi5MWwrWTqengY/edit Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/17Olunofp5EpxNJ0iq8Z8YLqK2KvF-uZx/edit#slide=id.p1
Presentation in the Earth System Science Stream at the 2023 Australasian Leadership Computing Symposium.	Rees, N., Wyborn, L., Yang, R., Hollmann, H., Croucher, J., Farrington, R., Sun, Y., Liu, Y., Robinson, A., Evans, B., 2023. A path towards reproducible MT time series processing on HPC. Australian Leadership Computing Symposium 2023, https://opus.nci.org.au/x/owW9D	Abstract: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wdM8aAWJvbnDYo-Lt-C4eKONV2AsM-3G7pcrWMj0Xdc/edit Presentation: https://opus.nci.org.au/display/ALCS/Earth+System+Science+-+Stream+Program?preview=/213714339/230490270/Nigel_Rees_15June2023.pdf
2030 Geophysics Collection Project: Leveraging RDA outputs and community	Presentation at “Planet Research Data Commons and the Impact of Being Involved in the RDA” webinar. Wyborn, L., Rees, N., Croucher, J., Hollmann, H., Farrington, R., Sun, Y., Liu, Y., Yang, R., Robinson, A. and Evans, B., 2023. 2030 Geophysics Collections Project: Leveraging RDA outputs and community. Presented at the Planet Research Data Commons and the “Impact of Being Involved in the RDA” webinar.	Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1h7XrVxC_zF0T26Puxt_d3tm3fsw8Y5NiBEA2nR8xLf0/edit#slide=id.g22b0279da71_0_0 Workshop details: https://www.eventbrite.com.au/e/planet-research-data-commons-and-the-impact-of-being-involved-in-the-rda-tickets-631271137967
Oral Presentation at the AESC 2023	Wyborn, L., Rees, N., Evans, B., Hollmann, H., Croucher, J., Farrington, R., Rawling, T., Yang, R., Sun, Y., 2023: Building the Australian National High-Resolution Geophysics Reference Collection to Prepare for Multi-physics Inversions at	Abstract: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1TH8cN87Seo49YIbIX5T5btJiUMyZZ4zdGXivYx4Q94/edit?usp=sharing Presentation:

	Exascale in 2030. 2023 Australian Earth Science Convention.	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1mKMatzRnPKasTkzvomBxSjaJr-9tCO0s/view?usp=sharing
Oral paper at eResearch 2023	Croucher, J., Hollmann, H., Liu, Y., Robinson, A., Rees, N., Farrington, R., Wyborn, L., and Evans, B. 2023. Vertical Integration of National Geophysical Data Assets to Support Next-generation Reproducible Research at Exascale. Abstracts, eResearch Australasia 2023.	Abstract: https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/vertical-integration-of-national-geophysical-data-assets-to-support-next-generation-reproducible-research-at-exascale/ Presentation https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/1420-Jo-Croucher.pdf
Oral paper by eResearch 2023	Rees, N., Yang, R., Sun, Y., Guo, E., Wyborn, L., and Evans, B., 2023. Preparing geophysical data and software for Exascale: A case study from the 2030 Geophysics Collections Project. Abstracts, eResearch Australasia 2023.	Abstract: https://conference.eresearch.edu.au/preparing-geophysical-data-and-software-for-exascale-a-case-study-from-the-2030-geophysics-collections-project/ Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1AmklqHkzDwwSOivi4aRlxG3y7C_6L5Y/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=116849426893249819316&rtpof=true&sd=true
SciDataCon 2023	Hollmann, H., Rees, N., Croucher, J., Evans, B., Farrington, R., Liu, Y., Wyborn, L., 2023. Towards transparent data-intensive computation in the Exascale era: An update from the 2030 Geophysics Collections project. Abstract, SciDataCon, 2023.	Abstract: https://www.scidatacon.org/IDW-2023-Salzburg/sessions/566/paper/1170/ Presentation: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/142RN1-W4J3ADH4OS-0Y4eMH66ZkQGiNKz8SO3o6vK1w/edit?usp=sharing
AGU Fall Meeting 2023	Wyborn, L., Prent, A., Croucher, J., Rees, N., and Farrington, R., 2023 Using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) to Accelerate Machine-to-machine Interoperability of Geoscience datasets Within and Across Repositories, Communities and Other Domains. Abstracts, AGU 2023 Fall	Abstract: https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm23/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/1440456

	Meeting.	
AGU Fall Meeting 2023	Rees, N., Wyborn, L., Yang, R., Hollmann, H., Croucher, J., Farrington, R., Sun, Y., Liu, Y., Evans., B., 2023 Working towards open science for Australian Geophysics: A case study from the 2030 Geophysics Collections Project. Abstracts, AGU 2023 Fall Meeting.	Abstract: https://agu.confex.com/agu/fm23/meetingapp.cgi/Paper/1384398
2023 Vocabulary Symposium	Wyborn, L., Croucher, J., Prent, A., Rees, N., and Farrington, R. Accelerating Machine-to-Machine Interoperability of Geoscience Data through using FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and FAIR Enabling Resources (FERs) to Declare Semantic Resources Implemented in any Dataset. Australian 2023 Vocabulary Symposium.	Abstract and Presentation: https://zenodo.org/records/10052244

5.2 Research Outcomes Planning

ACTIVITY	DETAILS
Establishment of a monitoring framework (for project outcomes and impacts)	Dr Laure Haak generated a one-page impact reporting plan for the Geophysics 2030 project in consultation with project representatives. A plan is in place for the completion of the ' Project Impact Report ' template at 12 and 24 months after project conclusion.
Inputs from research users in design of the infrastructure	As a collaborative project, input from research users has been fundamental to the design and execution of the project objectives.
Partnerships with research translation specialists	The Geophysics 2030 online and in-person training events have provided feedback on project outputs and enabled the translation of research to industry practitioners (e.g. attendees from BHP, state and territory geological surveys etc.).
Establishment of policies, systems and workflows to track uptake (of project outcomes)	The COUNTER trial and reporting requirements analysis completed as part of Work Package #7 have fed into NCI upgrade cycles, system developments and planning.
Other (please list)	The project team collaborated with Dr Laure Haak regarding an additional deliverable titled 'Summary of working models for impact tracking for exemplar NDA project (proof of concept)'.

6 LESSONS LEARNED

6.1 What Went Well?

ARDC support regarding metadata standards and interoperability between other organisations was a critical factor in supporting the success of this project. Particular thanks goes to Melanie Barlow and Rowan Brownlee for their generous expertise.

A number of infrastructure agreements were undertaken concomitantly with the proposal of the Geophysics 2030 project, including:

1. Establishment of AuScope's formal NCI share to support computational and data requirements;
2. Change of AuScope Contracts; and
3. Using RDA for integration of data assets from NCRIS facilities and other sources.

In addition, a number of software upgrades were influenced as a result of the Geophysics 2030 project, including:

1. Establishment of the NCI geophysics software modules;
2. Influence to the upgrade plan for the existing NCI Data Catalogue infrastructure; and
3. Exploration of new types of vocabulary integration in RVA.

6.2 What Could be Improved?

6.2.1 Lessons learnt for Earth and environmental research and infrastructure

- This project showed how the original forms of high resolution data taken directly from instruments in the field could so easily be lost. Although many derivative products are available online, in many cases the raw data is stored on hard drives and offline tapes. A concerted and ongoing effort needs to be made to ensure that legacy primary geophysical data sources are located and properly curated;
- The amount of effort and time required to “rescue” the raw field data, upgrade the metadata and convert to modern self describing formats was considerable. This mostly required effort from the data managers, but also from the researchers who originally collected the data. The project showed that although 2030 is still seven years off, if we want to use many existing geophysical datasets in exascale computing, we need to consider resourcing the rescue of legacy datasets now, otherwise they will be lost to Australian research forever;
- To take advantage of HPC to process raw and minimally processed data, as many attributes as possible collected in the field data should be “born digital” and “born connected” to agreed international standards for that data type. In several cases, these attributes are collected across multiple institutions

and the variability in data management practices observed through this project and the amount of effort expended to rescue legacy datasets was considerable. This underscores the value in investing in projects/collections/organisations mutually agreed standardised 'dirt to desktop' workflows prior to data collection;

- Although the MT community is starting to move to HDF5 based formats, other geophysical communities are yet to transition to HPC-enabled standards and formats. While legacy standards may still support current work practices and applications, scaling to data-intensive methods will require converting to modern self-describing formats. For example, there are movements internationally within the passive seismic community to explore several candidate modern self-describing standards. Lessons learnt in the conversion of the MT data within this project could be applicable to many other geophysical data types;
- This project also highlighted the need to distinguish between working formats and delivery formats. Much geophysical data is currently delivered by data producers in formats that are optimised towards delivery and data streaming options, mostly as images and data products and sometimes in proprietary formats. To use data on HPC, there is a need to focus on self describing formats that are also more suited to data archiving. Formats suitable for online GIS systems and dashboards are not necessarily suitable for data-intensive processing on HPC.
- Vertical integration of datasets is challenging as it requires coordination across multiple stakeholders and systems who use different standards and do not use PIDs consistently;
- The ability to horizontally integrate calibration data in real time from an external web service was proven for a small volume dataset. However, this could be limited by the size of the data being accessed in real time. Clearly very large volume datasets need to be accessed in-situ, but the size at which a dataset can still be effectively accessed remotely via web services is yet to be determined. However, it has become increasingly clear through our engagement with scientists that their preference is more aligned with in-situ access to data with a fully integrated software HPC-ready ecosystem. This significantly improves the ability to use the data to its fullest extent, increases the ability to foster community and hence collaborate more broadly with other researchers in the domain, and the expertise and support provided on the infrastructure;
- The project underscored calls for nuanced credit for data creators and contributors (e.g. [Parsons et. al., 2022](#)). Various schemas can be used to represent different roles within the data lifecycle, from data collection to curation ([Habermann, 2021](#)).
- Implementation of best-practice FAIR metadata principles can be constrained by the functionality of the available catalogue software. Dedicated projects focused on upgrading and enabling critical catalogue infrastructure would provide a range of benefits to the end-users and partners;
- To drive research innovation, infrastructure for PIDs needs to be facilitated by NCRIS Facilities. There is a particular need for PID services and support for non-dataset resources (e.g., instruments, calibrations, grants, samples, etc);

- Differences in metadata profiles, compliance with FAIR, ARDC Outputs requirements and target aggregator between ARDC programs added complexity to the project (DataCite vs RDA);
- Integration of metadata across NCRIS facilities and the geological surveys was constrained by differences in metadata and the lack of stable processes. Using RDA to aggregate data from many of the data providers for this project leveraged the existing functionality of RDA (e.g., cross-walking and integration of metadata, discovery etc.);
- To fully comply with the FAIR principles, publishing machine-readable vocabularies remains challenging. Options for publishing metadata schemas and associating PURLs or DOIs with vocabularies would be an advantage for publicly-accessible vocabulary services. Although some vocabularies have URIs for individual terms, few vocabularies and vocabulary services are identified by PIDs. This makes it difficult to specify exactly which vocabulary or vocabulary profile has been implemented in individual FIPs, and where assigned, FERs;
- Scientific practices around the creation and publishing of FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) remain in flux. Some FIP templates are only in Excel format and machine-readability is limited. To best support interoperability, FIPs need to be versioned and published with PURLs/DOIs;
- The project also explored implementation of the CARE principles. Although these principles are well enunciated, few groups appear to be implementing these at the dataset level and in the various ways required for our data science needs. Of particular relevance is how to: 1) provide the evidence that in the primary collection of geophysical datasets was in the field that the CARE principles have been adhered to; and, 2) how should adherence to the CARE principles be explicitly described in machine-actionable metadata. More details are explained in [Appendix 4 to this report](#) as to how NCI is addressing the CARE principles within the emerging developments of International Groups that are working on this issue; such as the [TRUST Code: A Global Code of Conduct for Equitable Research Partnerships](#). The TRUST Code recommends the inclusion of Global Research Collaboration Statements in the acknowledgements of scholarly publications (e.g. [Holt et al., 2023](#); [Sánchez-Gutiérrez et al., 2023](#); [Tully et al., 2023](#)), which need to include how the data supporting the paper comply with CARE and the interaction with local communities in collecting data on indigenous lands. We have also been following work on “Indigenous Metadata Bundles” by representatives from academia, museums, governmental agencies, and not-for-profit organisations across North America, Australia, Aotearoa/New Zealand, Europe, and French Polynesia who are seeking to define “Indigenous Metadata Bundles” to support the recognition and inclusion of Indigenous Peoples’ data ([Carroll et al., 2023a](#), [Carroll et al., 2023 b](#)). In the 2030 project our current efforts were focussed on trying to define in the metadata how the CARE principles were applied and also attach to the metadata the copies of agreements and notices within local contexts that were undertaken for MT surveys in the Musgraves and South Australia. It is also essential that these metadata elements are guaranteed to persist with the data and not be removed if the data are replicated and/or subsets moved to other repositories. The main stumbling block is that the required metadata bundlers are not well defined in the community; and

- The project also identified some issues relating to harvesting records from multiple catalogues. For large collaborative national projects, such as ASTER and Passive Seismic, there can be separate records of the datasets held in various data catalogues by other repositories, which can result in duplicates when harvested to RDA. Titles and descriptions in the source catalogues may be unique, but when aggregated in the RDA catalogue the different versions can be difficult for end-users to distinguish. This issue requires collaboration across all agencies that publish geophysical data in Australia and the coordination of best practice descriptions and definitions of fields such as; titles, abstracts, metadata profiles, etc.

6.2.2 Project management

- Delays in staff recruitment were a known risk for the project. However, this did not affect the overall delivery of the project and some early delays in the technical work were absorbed into the overall project delivery.
- Difficulty recruiting technical and data staff was always a risk, increasingly so with organisational changes outside the control of the project and not known when the project proposal was envisaged. As a result it delayed the commencement of some work within the project scope. However, these delays were able to be absorbed into the project over the full period. If the project was on an even shorter timeline, this would not have been possible.
- The careful recruitment of staff and the overheads in working through the transition and uplift of their skills then became more evident, significantly accelerating the project momentum and deepening the dimensions of technical improvements as time progressed.
- Reporting overheads impacted on resourcing to complete technical project tasks, particularly during the final stage of the project delivery.
- The project did not use dedicated project management resources as this was a minimally funded project with an overall small number of staff. The project focused on infrastructure innovation rather than larger community building or project reporting. As a result, the overall project delivered better scientific infrastructure as it was being guided by scientific researchers who could more easily adjust to the developing needs.

Appendices

- I. NCI Australia. (2023). NCI - Appendix 1 of Fair Guidelines for NDA Projects - Mapped metadata requirements across ARDC co-investment programs, ARDC Template. Available at: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1PVSCQyvKMIbDasitfYj8dNQTCxe_xyfr6dj2_6dOPCo/edit?usp=sharing
- II. NCI Australia. (2023). 2030 Geophysics XN002 - FAIR assessment - Aligns with First Section in FAIR Data Guidelines for Project Outputs, ARDC Template. Available at: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/10mjGcAUEvTnZVFbXNpwTFMHszHMHNiZ2FKz-ovtx6gl/edit?usp=sharing>
- III. NCI Australia. (2023). COUNTER Usage Metrics: National Computational Infrastructure - ARDC Project Report (1.0). NCI Australia. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8093111>
- IV. NCI Australia. (2023). Support for the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance: National Computational Infrastructure - ARDC Geophysics 2030 Project Report (v1.0). NCI Australia. Available at: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1xp8q2WRWW2ekMgYPGTu2DUwgeXq4b2f1Su0k0sGcJ1E/edit?usp=sharing>
- V. NCI Australia. (2023). Geophysics 2030 - UAT Summary: National Computational Infrastructure - ARDC Geophysics 2030 Project Report (v1.0) Report. NCI Australia. Available at: <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1YWM9SbHggaoNmRj3mLUqAFqio-o3KjemHG9HRhvcfQ/edit?usp=sharing>
- VI. NCI Australia (2023). Geophysics Community [website]. NCI Australia. Available at: https://opus.nci.org.au/x/bwC_Bg
- VII. NCI Australia (2023). NCI Reporting Requirements: National Computational Infrastructure - ARDC Geophysics 2030 Project Report (v1.0). NCI Australia. Available at: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Hms7IDEgILjriU3VqErEHf0_FYPBmAeqE47ljKdTvI/edit?usp=sharing
- VIII. NCI Australia (2022). NCI Data Catalogue Crosswalk. NCI Australia. Available at: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1nypHqJMUaB_Yerd6Qz8f4YfrivQCOi5v/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=103234877255333829233&rtpof=true&sd=true